

THE IMPACT OF CLIMATE CHANGE ON EDUCATION

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Annotation: This thesis examines how climate change affects education by disrupting school access, damaging infrastructure, and displacing students and teachers. It also explores the need for climate education and suggests strategies to build resilient education systems. The study uses case studies and existing research to highlight key impacts and solutions.

Keywords: climate change, education, school disruption, climate education, resilience, infrastructure, displacement.

Climate change has a direct impact on education. The primary impacts of climate change on education arise from the effects of extreme weather events, such as heavy rains accompanied by flash floods, strong winds and hail storms with short and long-term consequences. Drought and increasing temperatures lead to poor harvests and food scarcity which have negative impacts upon educational attainment.

Extreme weather events reduce the availability of safe drinking water, compromise sanitation and increase the incidence of weather related diseases such as malaria and diarrhoeal diseases, leading to absenteeism and possible withdrawal of children from school. Beside the primary impacts, climate change also has secondary impacts on education, arising from the ways in which households respond to, or choose to cope with and adapt to climate change as evidenced by income supplementing activities of household members, migration and child marriages.

These extreme weather events are increasingly disrupting schooling; precipitating learning losses, dropouts, and long-term impacts. The education of 75 million children is estimated to have been disrupted by conflict and natural disasters. These are projected to increase in frequency and severity with climate change. Over 99 percent of children around the world are exposed to at least one major climate and environmental hazard, shock. These are eroding education outcomes and recent progress in improving school access and learning.

Extreme weather events threaten learning, enrollment, and the future prospects of students through both direct and indirect channels. conflict, migration, and displacement. These indirect pathways. result in reduced

student readiness to learn due to health and nutrition shocks diminished demand for schooling due to household coping mechanisms, and disruption to education services due to displacement and conflict.

UCS analyzed how rising heat stress levels would affect students in the San Joaquin Valley, California as a case study of why climate-smart infrastructure is critical to protect children in a warming future. Many children in the region are at high risk of heat-related illness. Rising temperatures would reduce the window of time that it is safe for these children to be active outdoors, potentially disrupting health-promoting activities like exercise, further interrupting everyday life, and reinforcing the importance of reliable cooling and climate-safe infrastructure and school facilities. This analysis illustrates just one of many reasons that our schools must be prepared for a future of more climate extremes. Like many other types of infrastructure, schools have traditionally been designed and built using past climate and weather trends to predict the future. Previously, this assumption was reasonable, but global warming is making it increasingly invalid. Instead, the future will bring increased variability and longer, more frequent, and more intense heat waves, droughts, heavy precipitation and flooding. While the degree and type of impact may vary by location, no part of the nation will be left untouched. The crumbling state of our school facilities, which earned a “D+” from American Society of Civil Engineers, leaves them even more vulnerable to these impacts. Recent events like 2018’s Camp Fire in California remind us what can happen if school facilities are not ready. The fire resulted in the loss of more than 80 lives destroying schools and students’ homes, and, combined with concurrent fires in other parts of the state, its smoke led to the closure of more than 180 school districts across the state (with impacts on 1.1 million students). In recent weeks, Public Safety Power Shutoffs to prevent wildfires left many schools without power and no choice but to close. The impacts of a changing climate aren’t isolated to California. Schools without air conditioning in Baltimore and Columbus, Ohio, shut their doors during the record-breaking heatwave last month. Historic flooding in the Midwest this year led to the closing of nearly 20 school districts.

As climate-related events continue to increase in frequency and intensity, they create significant barriers to children’s educational success. Extreme weather conditions directly reduce learning capacity, with evidence showing that high temperatures and climate

disruptions can result in severe learning losses. The compounding effects of school closures, displacement and economic instability caused by climate-

induced disasters disproportionately affect the most vulnerable populations, including girls, children with disabilities, and children from low-income families. In some cases, as in Southeast Asia, East Asia and the Pacific Islands, entire communities are displaced, and children lose months or even years of schooling.

Teachers, too, are deeply affected by climate change. In regions hit by climate-induced disasters, they face immense challenges, including damaged infrastructure, overcrowded classrooms, and emotional and physical burdens. Their ability to teach is compromised, further affecting the learning outcomes of their students. The hardships that they face, which remain largely unreported, combined with insufficient training to address the specific needs of climate-displaced children, weaken the overall educational system's resilience, and their ability to teach effectively.

The role of education and education systems needs to be recognized as a critical tool in the regional response to climate change, and all components of an educational system must be retrofitted to respond effectively to future climate-induced disasters. Developing these transformative, climate-smart education systems that integrate climate change adaptation, mitigation, preparedness and resilience is essential globally and in the most climate-vulnerable EAP region. Most importantly, these education systems must be designed to equip children with the knowledge and skills to navigate and overcome the challenges posed by their changing environment. When education systems are climate-smart, they provide children with the capability to transform their futures and address future climate-induced disasters.

References:

- 1.Unicef for every child. Under pressure: The impacts of climate change on education in the East Asia and Pacific Region. United Nations Fund (UNICEF), March 2025.
- 2.Jamesine Rogers Gibson. Climate Change Affects Students' Well-Being: Case Study of Extreme Heat in San Joaquin Valley and Need for Climate-Smart Schools.November 7, 2019.
- 3.Sergio Venegas Marin, Lara Schwarz, and Shwetlena Sabarwal. The impact of climate change on education and what to do about it. April 2024.
- 4.Climate change and education. Zimbabwe Human Development Report 2017.

